

PLAYING GOD: INSIDE THE ROLE OF THE STAGE MANAGER

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As the curtain rises, the audience is greeted with the magical performance that is theater. Actors waltz across the stage, sets move, costumes capture your interest, and so much more. That is what is seen, but how does a theater production run so smoothly? Or the better question is, who is responsible for making theater run smoothly?

The answer is simple, it is the Stage Manager. My role in theatre is a Stage Manager, just like how other people are actors or designers.

The long answer is more complicated. According to Laurie Kinckman, "A cleaning house for information, the stage manager is responsible for organizing rehearsals and running performances... the stage manager might be thought of as the 'air-traffic controller' of a theatrical production, coordinating the flow of information into and out of the theatre and guiding the participants to a finished product that reflects the artistic considerations of all" (5). Roth, Allender-Zivic, and McGlaughlin defined a stage manager as, "one of the few individuals with whom all members of the company interact and, as such, becomes a confidant, a coach, a peacekeeper, and a friend" ("Stage Management Basics").

The Stage Manager is an essential but not a widely known part of the theater. During the Fall 2021 semester, I was assigned to be the stage manager for CSUF's College of the Arts production of *The SpongeBob Musical*. I learned first-hand what being a stage manager is and my importance to the theater.

As stage managers, we are used to giving a very basic and not fully encompassing explanation of our job when asked. When I was given *The SpongeBob Musical*, I knew that I had an opportunity to fully explore this question which had always given me trouble explaining to people both outside and inside the theater.

The answer I always gave was that the stage manager is the right-hand man to the director and the primary connection of communication between the theater departments. While this answer is true, it is a vague explanation and leaves out so much. In this project, I explore what the stage manager's job is to the fullest extent and shed light on how important stage managers are to the production.

I. Pre-Production

The start of it all is the pre-production. Pre-production is all the work that must be done before the first rehearsal. For the stage manager, this is a vital time. A professional Stage manager would normally begin pre-production one week before rehearsals. Luckily, I had the chance to get started in July of 2021. I had to read the play, prepare the scene breakdown, make templates for my paperwork, and have meetings with my director and assistant stage managers.

Preparing the scene breakdown is what took up most of my pre-production time. Before I began the scene breakdown, I read through the script. After reading the script, I reread it, but this time while filling out my breakdown.

A scene breakdown is the tracking of which characters are on stage and when they exit and enter. This paperwork is used not only by me but also by the director and designers. Because of this, I started and finished this document first before I began any other. My director for the musical, Sarah Ripper, used my scene breakdown to help her with casting. Ripper would consult my breakdown while double-casting people to ensure there was no overlap of the two characters they were playing and ensuring the actor had enough time for a costume change. Costumes were able to use my breakdown and figure out which costume pieces needed to be rigged for a quick change. It was also used to figure out what roles the swings would be covering and what they could not cover. A swing is a performer who covers multiple roles in the ensemble and is used when an actor is unable to perform or when an actor has a night off.

My scene breakdown was a widely used document that helped multiple departments. Linked is my [Scene Breakdown](#).

The templates I made were the daily call, rehearsal report, production report, and contact sheet. I needed this to be done before the first rehearsal because I would need to use three out of

the four during the first rehearsal. The performance report template did not need to be completed until a few days before the run of the show, but I had wanted to get it out of the way while I still had time to spare.

Linked are my templates for the [Daily Call](#), [Rehearsal Report](#), [Performance Report](#), and [Contact Sheet](#). I will explain what each of these documents is used for in greater detail later.

One of the last parts of my pre-production was my first initial meetings with my director and ASMs. During the meeting with the director, she told me about her vision for the show, the expectations she had of me, and the rules for the rehearsal room. In turn, I also had questions I had prepared beforehand for her. These questions included:

- *Do you have any specific details regarding the costumes or props that are not in the script?*
- *Are there any needs you would like during rehearsals, such as specifics in the rehearsal room or food, coffee, tea, etc.?*
- *For the rehearsal process in terms of breaks, do you like to work for 80 minutes and take a 10-minute break or work for 55 minutes and take a 5-minute break?*
- *Is there anything you will need or expect from me?*

Ripper answered my questions, and I felt I better understood what environment she intended to create and what she expected of me.

I had a separate meeting with my assistants, in which I told them my expectations of them during rehearsal, tech, and the show. I made it very clear that I wanted the stage management team to function as professionals do in the industry, and to make our power dynamics very clear so none of us would be doing each other's job. I made sure they knew what conversation and communication was appropriate with the director and what was not. For example, assistants

directly texting the director questions was not ok. I wanted them to understand that I was the stage manager, and they were my assistants, which meant I was having crucial conversations with the director and designer, not them. I also made sure they knew I was here to help them and that I was willing to look over their paperwork and even provide them with my past ASM paperwork they could use as a guide.

Another important point I wanted to drive home was that I wanted our stage management team to be a safe space for all three of us. Being on the stage management team would be stressful, so I wanted to create a safe space where we could air out our frustrations and know it stayed between the three of us. I ended our meeting by asking if they had any questions about their roles, and I answered any questions they had.

I also used this pre-production time to start putting together my prompt book. The prompt book, also known as the stage manager bible, is a binder full of all the paperwork the stage manager makes and additional documentation. In my prompt book, I had ten sections separated by dividers: Calendar, Contact Sheet, Script, Key, Scene Breakdown, Scenic, Daily Calls, Rehearsal Reports, Performance Reports, and Accident Reports. I added the documents into my prompt book throughout the rehearsals, tech, and performances. My prompt book would not be finished and turned into my mentor until a week after the last performance.

The last, but not least, of my duties during pre-production was putting together my stage management box. My stage management box was full of items that may be needed during the rehearsals and production. These items included pencils, sticky notes, pads/tampons, Ibuprofen/Tylenol, hairbrush, deodorant, etc. My box was intended to be prepared for any needs outside of a first aid kit that either I, my assistants, the director, or the cast may need during rehearsals or the run of the show. The downside of making a stage management box was that it

was required, but I had to make it all with my own money. I was very grateful to have had the means to purchase and put my box together. Starting the first day of rehearsal, I brought my stage management box to every rehearsal and show.

II. Rehearsal

During the first rehearsal, also known as the First Rehearsal Meeting, I gave a speech to the cast I had prepared a few days prior. The first rehearsal speech is done in professional theaters and is always given by the stage manager. In my speech, I introduced myself— including my pronouns— and my assistants, along with what each of them would be focusing on. One assistant would focus on sets/props and the other on costumes/makeup/wigs. I then went over a few logistics with the actors, which included what class section to sign up for, the rules of the rehearsal room (no food, no using phones, homework allowed while not working, etc.), and emphasized the need for them to prioritize making the rehearsal and performance spaces focused because there was lots of work to be done. At that moment, I passed around the contact sheet and had all the actors make sure their names and contact information were correct. Once the contact sheet was handed back to me, I went over important dates in the calendar so everyone knew and there would be no confusion or misunderstanding. Some of these dates included our one Saturday rehearsal, the first day of tech, opening and closing performance days, etc. I then proceeded to go over the current COVID-19 protocols and safety measures in case of a fire, earthquake, or active shooter. The last portion of my speech was electing a Company Deputy and explaining to the cast what the duties of that position were. I had the production team leave the room, and I asked for any volunteers from the cast, of which three showed interest and had an anonymous vote. Once the Company Deputy was elected, the production team was let back inside the room.

My first rehearsal speech was finished and, in my eyes, a success. The rest of the first rehearsal was used to pass out scripts, allow designers to show the cast their designs, and have a read-through of the musical.

Now that rehearsals had officially started, my time-consuming work began. I would arrive an hour or earlier to the start of each rehearsal. Before that time, I would prepare and have a small meeting with the director in which we would go over what was to happen during the rehearsal. Thirty minutes before the start of rehearsal, my assistants would arrive and set up for that night's rehearsal— this included grabbing props, setting up worktables, setting up the Foley Artist's table, and rearranging rehearsal blocks that were used to represent set pieces.

The rehearsal started right at 7 o'clock, and the director would begin the blocking. Blocking is instructions given to the actor on where and how they move onstage. My main job during rehearsal was to write down the blocking. Some scenes were simple; others were complex. I also wrote down the choreography into my blocking script because I saw it as a significant movement onstage. The director and actors knew I had the blocking recorded and would often come to me asking questions on blocking that they missed or did not understand.

Linked are examples of my [Blocking](#). I used a software program called Stage Write to create my blocking. I will explain the software in greater detail later.

Recording the blocking took up most of my time in and outside of rehearsal. I would constantly add, fix, or erase blocking as the director changed what she originally had. Having the most updated blocking was important not only for the actors and me but for the lighting designer, who needed to know precisely where the actors were onstage so he could light the stage correctly.

However, blocking was not the only thing I was doing during the rehearsals. I had to keep track of time and make sure everyone received a break according to equity rules: after eighty minutes, a ten-minute break, or after fifty-five minutes, a five-minute break. This rule can be found under Rule 50 section B (1) in the "Actor's Equity Association." I made sure these break

rules were being followed because I wanted to ensure no one was taken advantage of during the show process. As the stage manager, I advocate for the actors and my assistants, which means I look out for them and make sure they are getting the treatment they deserve. These treatments include breaks after the appropriate times.

I also had to keep updating my rehearsal report document throughout the whole rehearsal. The rehearsal report is a document made by the stage manager that covers what happened at rehearsal, questions or requests for specific departments, and attendance. This report was sent out every night before I left the rehearsal space, and it was distributed to everyone on the production team (director, designers, production staff, and faculty mentors.). In total, I had made thirty-six rehearsal reports.

Linked are examples of my [Rehearsal Reports](#).

After each rehearsal, my ASMs would clean up while I had another small meeting with my director or talked with an actor— usually regarding questions about blocking, the schedule, or costume fittings. My small meeting with my director was when we would both go over my daily call and add or erase anything to it. The daily call is a document made by the stage manager that tells the actors—and later during tech the crew— what time they are called, and it is sent every night prior to the rehearsal to allow the actors to be prepared for the next rehearsal. Also, in the daily call was a tentative schedule of what was happening the next day in rehearsal. I needed to send out the daily call before I left the rehearsal room or twelve hours before the next rehearsal, or else the actors could claim I did not give them enough notice in advance about their call time for the next day. This is another equity rule the CSUF Theatre department follows, which can be found under Rule 51 section C (1).

Linked are examples of my [Daily Calls](#).

The whole rehearsal process was six weeks, and this is a good overview of what I did during that time. Outside of rehearsals, I was in weekly production meetings where the whole production team— director, choreographer, lighting designer, props master, set designer, sound designer, costumes designer, makeup/wigs designer, technical director, me, and all our assistants— would give updates and ask and answer questions. I was also in separate meetings with designers to go over more specifics and figure out logistics. These specifics and logistics included costume changes, adding and removing sets and props, special rigging, and further design questions for the director. I was usually the one to set up these meetings via Zoom. Any information that needed to be passed to other departments I passed along. I spent an average of six hours a day working on the show during the rehearsal process, most of that time being the actual rehearsals and the outside meetings.

In the two last weeks of rehearsal, I started my end of rehearsal process. This was when I made sure everything was as prepared as possible before going into tech. I went over my assistant's paperwork—set tracking, costume tracking, prop tracking, and run sheet— to make sure it was ready and had them add missing information. Any information I was missing I sought out after; this included unresolved blocking and design decisions. I also added the crew to my Contact Sheet, finally completing my document.

Linked is my completed [Contact Sheet](#). Please note that phone numbers were redacted.

But most importantly, I made sure the first draft of my script was ready, so I could write in cues whenever the designers gave them to me during tech.

III. Tech

Tech week, the moment where I am in control with a splash of chaos. Tech week is when the show is moved out of the rehearsal room and onto the stage. At this point, the set, costumes, wigs, and props should be finished and only changed or altered at the director's request or if it does not work. This part of the theater show process is stressful because it is the first time all the departments come together with their final products and put them together to create a show. Putting it all together is not smooth at first, but there is only a limited amount of time for it to become audience ready. As the stage manager, I am in charge of leading tech and pushing the process forward.

My tech was eight days long and consisted of a Company Meeting, Staging/Light Over, Sitzprobe, standard tech rehearsals, a 10 out of 12, and a Final Dress. The first night of tech was Company Meeting, which was the first time all the actors, the production team, and the crew met in one place. I started the week of tech by giving my Company Meeting speech, which is another standard practice in professional theaters.

I introduced myself and my pronouns in my speech, and I also introduced my assistants. I then introduced the rest of the production team, so the cast and crew knew who the director and designers were. I then went over important dates for tech and performances, ensuring everyone knew when our 10 out of 12 was, when our opening and closing were, when the ASL Interpreters would be here, and when the performances would be live-streamed. Then like in my first rehearsal speech, I went over the current COVID-19 protocols and safety measures in case of a fire, earthquake, or active shooter. Next, I gave a quick tour of the stage. I told everyone about the one automated set-piece, the Dooms Day Clock, and how it tracked. It was up in the air and tracked SL (stage left), SR (stage right), and disappeared UP (upstage) when need be. I also told

them of our big set pieces and big prop pieces that needed to be manually moved by actors or crew members, including SpongeBob's Pineapple, Patrick's Rock, Squidward's House, and Patrick's couch, etc. I then told them that there were quite a few flats on our rail system that fly in, such as the Bandshell and the Volcano. This was just a general overview, so everyone got the idea of what they would be working with during tech and the shows.

The crews broke off to learn about their jobs during the show, and I took the cast back up to the rehearsal space to finish some last-minute blocking. After an hour and a half, we returned to the stage to figure out what we could and could not do with actors on top of moving scaffolding and ladder units. That took the rest of the night, and I went home with one successful tech rehearsal under me.

Next was Staging/Light Over, where we spaced the more significant musical numbers and allowed our lighting designer to see where they would be placed onstage. Again, another essay day, and I only had to make a few adjustments to my blocking. Sitzprobe was the next rehearsal on the schedule. Sitzprobe is a rehearsal specifically for the orchestra and actors, who play and sing together for the first time, which meant it was downtime for me to finish my last touch-ups on my paperwork. I did not know it then, but Sitzprobe would be my last easy and feel-good tech rehearsal.

The rest of the tech week was the most challenging part of the whole process for me. It was the first time I questioned my ability to do my job, and made me feel unqualified. It started during our standard tech rehearsals when I made the mistake of printing my draft script front and back instead of one-sided. This was bad because I could not quickly flip my pages to read the next cues, instead, I had to move my head to the left, which took more time than I had to call the next cues. I felt I was given no mercy when I missed a cue I was calling for the first time. I

would hear aggressive, toned phrases thrown at me, such as "Why did you call it there?"

"Wrong, again." "Are you not understanding?" from the lighting designer constantly throughout the rehearsal. My mentor, who was not wearing a headset, must have seen the distress on my face because he suggested I call a break. I did just that and spent my break crying.

I felt out of control and did not think the other designers listened to me. Looking back on it, this was one of the negative aspects of having faculty designers. There is an already built power dynamic, and me being a student stage manager, I did not receive the respect I deserved. I was overlooked and spoken over. I am a very strong-willed person, and yet this still occurred. I am very fortunate to have had a director and mentor who were by my side to guide me through this mess. Luckily, there was only one faculty designer, the rest were students, so I was not wrestling with multiple people who only saw me as a student and not a stage manager.

After rehearsal that same night, I stayed in the theater space by myself until one in the morning, working on fixing my script and writing the cues I was given that day. Once that was done, I closed the whole theater and left. However, that night was not the end of the ugly side of tech. The feeling of not being good enough continued and would not stop until opening night.

My next big challenge of tech was the 10 out of 12 rehearsal. A 10 out of 12 is a rehearsal that is twelve hours long with a two-hour dinner break, usually from 10 am to 10 pm. This is the rehearsal where we cover most of the show so that the designers, specifically the lighting designer, can make sure everything looks correct and functions the way it needs to be. There were many stops and starts in my 10 out of 12 because the lighting designer had many cues to fix. This was due to many downstage shifts —moving the actors further down the stage— that the director made last minute. However, because of how slow everything was moving, many people, including the actors, started to get snappy at my assistants and me. Despite that, I was

told by my mentor that I was doing well with pushing the rehearsal along and keeping everyone on track. That day we ended on the third to last scene of the final act, which was unfortunately not where I had planned for us to end. This meant that our next rehearsal, which was supposed to be a run-through where I got to call the show for the first time, was not going to happen. I did not leave the theater until two hours after everyone had left to work on my calling script. I was exhausted and drained.

I got one day of break before our next rehearsal, the second to last, rolled around. During this rehearsal, we finished working through the last two scenes of the musical and then went over choreography, which was the actor's biggest challenge in this show. We did not get to do a run-through like initially planned.

The Final Dress rehearsal crept up, the first time we would run the whole show. The first time the actors would have performed the entire show with no stops. I would be calling the show for the first time without needing to stop for the director or lighting designer to fix something. This was my first rehearsal, and I was nervous. I called the show and made many mistakes. But I jotted down where the cue needed to be called and kept going. After two and a half hours of calling, my body was physically exhausted, but I had done it. I once again did not leave the theater until two hours after everyone else, and I was up an additional three more hours at my apartment fixing and finalizing my calling script.

Tech was rough and full of challenges, but I learned from the challenges, making me a better stage manager.

IV. Performance

Tech was finally over. All the cast, crew, and production teams' hard work had led to this; my hard work had led to this: opening the show. Opening night was when I became the "God" of the production. The night started well, everything was running smoothly and on time – fight call, lift call, lighting check, prop check, set check, actors in costume and makeup, and actors getting into mics. But I was still out of my mind nervous. It was now my show, every mistake that happened, regardless of who made it, was my fault.

I ran the fight and lift call while the lighting crew went through cues before opening the house. If there are staged fights and lifts, they must be run through with the actors once before every performance. For this production, I was the Fight Captain. I had the actors run the fight or lift at twenty-five percent speed, then fifty, then seventy, and finally full out speed. Once I was done with my fight/lift call and lighting was also done, I had the grand drape— curtain— fly in, and I handed the house over to the House Manager. Handing the house over or opening the house means the audience is let inside the theater. This usually happens thirty minutes before the start of the show.

Once the house was open, I headed up to my booth and waited. I gave place times, and my assistants made sure to give those place times to the actors and crew who could not hear me via my com set. I would always give the actors and crew the following places: one hour till places, thirty minutes till places, fifteen minutes till places, ten minutes till places, five minutes till places, and places. "Places" is when the actors and crew must be where they need to be to begin the performance. Actors and crew members are told by the stage management team when to go to places and how much time they have before places. At five minutes till places, I would do a com check to make sure all my board operators and assistants were ready. Once I called places, I

would wait until the House Manager handed me over the house. Once they gave me the house, I would begin the show.

Every single time before I called the first cue, my stomach would drop. But especially opening night when it was only my second time calling through the whole show. I took a deep breath, turned on my com, and became the God.

A lot goes into calling a show. There is a lot of responsibility and pressure because your words are commands. Calling cues at the exact moment is vital and affects how the show is presented to and preserved by the audience. I was in charge of calling light, sound, automation, projection, and rail cues at the exact moments in the show where the designers wanted them. I had around five hundred and thirty cues to call during *The SpongeBob Musical*. When I say "Go," that is when the cue is taken. Most of my cues were a verbal "Go," but all my rail cues were given off a cue light. The cue light I used was a small box with buttons that I would press to signal a visual "Go" to my rail operators who did not have a com to hear my verbal "Go." A more detailed function of the cue light is expanded on later. I also used the cue light to signal to the Conductor that we were about to start both at the beginning of the show and when intermission was over.

Not only was I calling cues, but I was also giving "Warns." A warn is a standby for the operators to know what cues are coming up next and to be prepared. My goal was to give the warns at least a page before. That was not a probable goal for lighting cues because there were so many compared to the other cues. Instead, I would give lighting warns when I had a big enough break, and their warns would contain more cues. For example, I would say, "Warn for light cues 76 through 111 and sound cues 10 through 13.5."

Linked is a small clip of me [Calling the Show](#) and a small portion of my [Calling Script](#).

The stage manager is called the God of the production because they make all the actions happen. Every light movement, sound effect, automation movement, and projection are being called at each exact moment by me, the stage manager. The only words that matter behind the scenes are when I say "Go." I am calling all the shots. I am making sure the integrity of the show is maintained. Everyone comes to me for answers and questions. Everyone listens to me, and my commands are final. It is a job full of power, but it needs to be led by a leader, not a dictator. I strived to be a leader that my cast and crew could confide in and trust. I hope to establish this trust when the cast and crew first meet me, but I especially hope they trust me when I take over the show opening night. And I honestly believe my cast and crew trusted me to lead them through the show.

Opening night was not perfect, and I tried not to beat myself up about it. I had to contently remind myself that opening night was only the second time I had ever called the show—which is not normal! I had to remind myself that I was not given the proper time to rehearse my part whenever I thought about my mistakes. It was hard, but I forgave myself for the mistakes and made sure they would not happen again tomorrow.

The second performance started smoothly with my fight and lift calls. I gave the house over to the House Manager and headed to the booth. I watched the crowd start coming in when suddenly, I heard a loud crack from behind the grand drape. Over the com, I hear my assistant in charge of sets tell me with an anxious voice that the top of SpongeBob's house had broken. She then proceeded to tell me what happened, and I immateriality jumped into action. I contacted the set designer, prop master, and faculty production manager to see if they had keys to the scenic lab to fix the snapped leaves. Luckily, the props master and production manager answered and were backstage in no time, rigging the leaves back to stay upright. They did a fantastic job for

the time limit they had, and you wouldn't have noticed the break unless you were up onstage.

After the performance, I made sure to put a general description in my performance report of what occurred and then separately emailed the appropriate parties a detailed description and who was involved.

During the run of a show, I had to continue making a daily call. Additionally, I had to make a performance report, which served the same function as the rehearsal report but for the performances. I would also add if any costumes, props, or set pieces broke and information regarding the size of the audience and their reactions.

Linked are examples of my [Performance Reports](#).

The third performance went well. I felt good calling the show, and there was only one costume malfunction that occurred— so a successful night. On the fourth night, closing night, I faced another challenge. Fourteen minutes into the second act, my rail cue lights stopped working. My rail operators— who control the flat sets that fly in and out— did not have a com, so I could not give them a verbal cue like I did my other operators. Instead, they had a light that I controlled that went off. When the red light turned on, it meant a warning and to stand by. When the red light went out, that signaled "Go." My operators had no idea when to bring the rails in without my rail cue light. I quickly and calmly told my assistant in charge of sets to stand by the operators, and I would give her the verbal "Go," and she would tell them to go. It was not an ideal situation, but it worked. I would be lying if I did not admit my heart dropped when the rail cue lights stopped responding, but I kept my head and continued forward because the show must go on. And it did.

Closing night was a success despite the challenges that sprang up. My cast, crew, and assistants did a fantastic job throughout all four shows. I was proud of the art they helped create.

After I put my self-criticizing hat away, I was proud of myself and my work as the stage manager on CSUF's production of *The SpongeBob Musical*.

V. Stage Write

During my time as the stage manager on *The SpongeBob Musical*, I got a unique opportunity. The CSUF Theatre and Dance department started licensing Stage Write's stage management software. I was the first stage manager in my department to use Stage Write for my paperwork. The paperwork I would use Stage Write for was my blocking and my calling script. I was allowed to use the software because I had been trained on it in my Advance Stage Management class the semester prior. I was very excited to use the program because stage managers on Broadway use Stage Write.

Linked is a small clip of me showing the functions of [Stage Write](#).

I am very grateful I got to be trained on and practically use Stage Write. A large chunk of my time was on that software during the rehearsal and tech process.

VI. What is the Stage Manager?

The stage manager is the actor's advocator, protector of the show, and the liaison between all aspects of the production. The stage manager upholds the integrity of the show that the director created. They document everything that happens both in the rehearsal room and onstage. They support and lead.

The stage manager strives to be an advocate, protector, and collaborator while being the God of the production. The job requires organization, excellent communication, and the ability to handle any type of person with respect. They must be able to handle the high stresses thrown at them and respond calmly with a solution.

Stage managers also must have knowledge in every theater field to communicate and understand their directors and designers. Being a stage manager is being a mini expert in lighting, sound, costumes, makeup, sets, props, and the list goes on. They must be able to articulate their thoughts and wants clearly; otherwise, their fellow collaborators will not be able to do their jobs effectively.

The stage manager is a vital component of a theater production. Without one, the show would fall apart.

What is the stage manager? The answer is simple: me.

What I had hoped to get from this experience was a better answer to tell people when they ask me what I do for a living. Subconsciously I knew what I did and my responsibilities, but I had never fully explained all that I did before to anyone, not even myself. I wanted an answer to the question, but what I got was a deeper understanding of myself and my importance to the theater.

My goal in life is to be a professional stage manager, and my ultimate dream is to be a Broadway stage manager. Through this project, I was able to go through being a stage manager on a big-scale production and later examine what I did during the whole process. The project allowed me to closely look at aspects of my job I had never truly looked at before and learned. I learned more about my job and learned from my mistakes, which has made me a better stage manager.

I have gained knowledge through this project that has helped me be better at my job.

Hopefully, in the future, when you're seeing a Broadway show and looking through your program, you'll find my name:

Production Stage Manager, *Kaylee Mesa*.

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